

Penetration of esters, derived from vegetable oils, for friction reduction

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INTRODUCTION

Rapidly advancing metathesis processes yield a variety of esters, which can be manufactured from vegetable oils or Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME). Esters, produced from non-food oils, such as Crambe and Camelina, are of particular interest. Dicarboxylic linear unsaturated α - ω methyl esters can be produced by FAME self-metathesis. Their transesterification with 2-ethyl hexanol (2EH) and other branched alcohols can lead to compounds, which are more effective than mineral oils in lubricant-related parameters [1]. In addition, they can act as nanopore fillers for anodized alumina by penetrating into the coating and assuring formation of a lubricant layer in the friction zone [2].

Penetration into Hydraulic Fluid (HF) market is especially promising, because some dibasic esters have already established themselves as viable HF basestocks. Saturated diesters such as di-2EH azelate (C9:0) and di-2EH sebacate (C10:0) have been used there for several decades. Recent developments [3] show that monounsaturated diesters can lead to improved fluidity, lower volatility, slower heat-thinning and many other desirable properties. Influence of the double bonds on lubricity is less evident and thus pursued here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tribotests were performed using Ducom™ (Fig. 1) and TRM-500™ (Fig. 2) tribometers for low and high speeds respectively, see Table 1.

Fig. 1. Ball-on-plate and ball-on-disc setup on Ducom tribometer

Fig. 2. D4172 4-ball setup on TRM-500 tribometer

Saturated (C10:0 and C12:0) and mono-unsaturated (C18:1) diester basestocks (Scheme 1) were blended with functional additives. Commercial hydraulic fluids (HF) of ISO VG32 grade (HF Q83) and VG46 grade (HF TR4) were acquired from distributors and tested for comparison. They were based on mineral oils, HF Q83 also contained Zinc dialkyl dithiophosphate (ZDDP) additives.

HYDRAULIC FLUID FORMULATION

HF must have good Anti-Wear (AW) and corrosion inhibition properties, resistance to oxidation. AW additives phosphorothioate and thiocarbamate (Scheme 2) were mixed at 1.5% wt. each into the diester basestocks.

Scheme 2. AW additives, used at 1.5% each

Dicyclohexyl amine, benzotriazole and thiadiazole were added at 0.1% wt. each as corrosion inhibitors, while hindered phenol at 0.5% wt. as Anti Oxidant (AO), Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Corrosion inhibitors and AO

FRICION AND WEAR RESULTS

HF pump tests are usually employed to evaluate basestocks and additives on friction and wear, but laboratory tests can successfully simulate pump test conditions [4]. Three different tribotesting regimes were used in this study, Table 1. HF performed poorer than esters in both starved regimes, but better in high speed D4172. Viscosity didn't correlate to wear or friction, Fig. 4.

Table 1. Tribotest conditions, oil viscosities at 40°C and their effects on wear. Underlined runs displayed in Fig. 3.

	Ball-on-plate	Ball-on-disc	4-ball D4172	
Movement	reciprocal	rotary	rotary	
Ball diameter	6 mm	6 mm	12.7 mm	
Load per ball	100 N	100 N	49 N	
Approx. velocity	2 cm/s	20 cm/s	400 cm/s	
Temperature	20-25°C	20-25°C	75°C	
Total sliding distance, flood	200 m, partially starved	200 m, partially starved	18 000 m, fully flooded	
Lubricants	Wear scar diameters, μm			mm²/s
C10:0 diester	747, 726	1030, <u>906</u>		11.6
C12:0 diester	539, 580, 652	720, 710	1044, <u>1068</u> , 1041	14.7
C18:1 diester	685, 683* 686* 688*	730, 725	849, <u>834</u>	34.1
HF Q83	668, 681, 683, 912	922, 1040	<u>297</u> , 296	32
HF TR4	1246, 1337, 983	1057, 1024	<u>660</u> , 277, 286, <u>295</u>	46

* formulation without dicyclohexyl amine and thiadiazole

Fig. 3. Wear scars of 4-ball specimens after testing diesters and HF.

** duplicate runs of HF TR4

Fig. 4. Friction trends of diesters and HF during the 4-ball test

CONCLUSIONS

- Penetration of dibasic esters into lubricant market can benefit from their better friction reduction properties, compared to mineral oils. Fig. 4 shows that during early tribotest stages C18:1 diester has lower friction than mineral oil hydraulic fluids TR4 and Q83
- Formulation with ashless AW additives can make esters comparable to HF in protection against wear, even to lubricants, which contain highly effective AW additives, e.g. ZDDP
- Mono-unsaturated C18:1 diester shows lower wear scars than saturated C10:0 or C12:0 diesters under high velocity tribotesting regime

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The project COSMOS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 635405. 4-ball tribotests were supervised by Prof. Juozas Padgurskas (Vytautas Magnus University, Kaunas)

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COSMOS
 ADDING VALUE TO CAMELINA AND CRAMBE OIL

ISSN 1822-7759

*Book of Abstracts
of the 21st International Conference-School*

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Programme

August 19, Monday

14:00 – 20:00 Arrival and registration

August 20, Tuesday

Chairman – Sigitas Tamulevičius

8:30 – 9:00 Registration

9:00 – 9:15 Opening

9:15 – 10:00 **Brant Gibson** (RMIT University, Australia)
Nanoscale BioPhotonics: Using Nanomaterials and Light to Understand the Inner Workings of the Body

10:00 – 10:45 **Albert G. Nasibulin** (Skolkovo Institute of Science and Technology, Russia)
Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes: from Synthesis to Applications

10:45 – 11:15 **Yesong Gu** (Tunghai University, Taiwan)
Fabrication of a Biocompatible and Continuous Glucose Biosensor with the Poly(3,4-Ethylenedioxythiophene) Modified Electrode

11:15 – 11:35 Coffee Break

11:35 – 12:20 **Luca Gregoratti** (Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste SCpA, Italy)
Nanomaterials Characterization at (Near) Ambient Pressure: Current Status and Perspectives of Scanning Photoemission Imaging

12:20 – 13:05 **Tadas Paulauskas** (Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Lithuania)
Development of Bismide-Based Multi-Junction Solar Cells

13:05 – 13:50 **Simas Račkauskas** (Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania)
Non-Catalytic Growth of Nanowires: Insights from *in-situ* TEM Investigation

13:50 – 18:00 Break

18:00 – 21:00 Welcome Party

August 21, Wednesday

Chairman – Kęstutis Grigoras

- 8:30 – 9:00** **Registration**
- 9:00 – 9:45** **Witold Brostow** (University of North Texas, USA)
Polymeric Materials and Their Applications
- 9:45 – 10:30** **Sergei V. Kostjuk** (Belarusian State University, Belarus)
Cationic Polymerization in Aqueous Media
- 10:30 – 11:00** **Xing Xing** (Northwestern Polytechnical University, China)
Device Engineering for High Performance Polymeric Electrochromism
- 11:00 – 11:20** **Coffee break**
- 11:20 – 12:05** **Karine Mougín** (Institut de Science des Matériaux de Mulhouse, France)
Surface Color on Demand
- 12:05 – 12:50** **Polina P. Kuzhir** (Belarusian State University, Belarus)
Graphene/Carbon Based Multilayers and Metasurfaces for THz and Microwave Application
- 12:50 – 13:35** **Linas Minkevičius** (Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Lithuania)
Compact Diffractive Optics for Terahertz Imaging Applications
- 13:35 – 16:00** **Meeting of Mutual funds Taiwan – Latvia – Lithuania Tripartite Cooperation Program project “2D nanostructures of noble metal nanoparticles for biosensor applications”**
- 16:00 – 22:00** **Social Event (Including Basketball Tournament and Other Competitions)**

August 22, Thursday

Chairman – Gil Rosenman

- 8:30 – 9:00** **Registration**
- 9:00 – 9:45** **Andrei V. Malkov** (Loughborough University London, United Kingdom)
Solution Processed CZTS Solar Cells: Chemistry of the Dissolution Process and Device Fabrication
- 9:45 – 10:30** **Kęstutis Grigoras** (VVT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd, Finland)
Porous Silicon Based Supercapacitors
- 10:30 – 10:50** **Coffee break**
- 10:50 – 11:50** **Hubert Halbritter** (OSRAM Opto Semiconductors GmbH, Germany)
The Light of the Future is Smart
- 11:50 – 12:35** **Sebastian Rothe** (CERN, Switzerland)
Engineering of Materials for Radioisotope Production at CERN-ISOLDE
- 12:35 – 13:20** **Alexander Petrov** (The National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Belarus)
Sr₂FeMoO_{6-δ} Double Perovskite Metal-Oxide Ferrimagnetic as a Prospective Material for Spintronic Applications
- 13:20 – 15:30** **Break**
- 15:30 – 17:30** **Poster Session** *Chairman – Tomas Tamulevičius*
15:30 – 16:20 Poster Session I (P1 – P61)
16:35 – 17:25 Poster Session II (P62 – P122)
- 17:30 – 18:00** **Conference Photo, Awards and Certificates**

August 23, Friday

Chairman – Simas Račkauskas

- 9:00 – 10:00** **Ashok Vaseashta** (The State University of New Jersey, USA)
**Smart and Connected Unmanned Aerial Surveillance
Nano-Sensor Based Platforms – Platform and Project**
- 10:00 – 10:45** **Gil Rosenman** (Tel Aviv University, Israel)
**Peptide Photonics: From Bioinspired Nanodots to Precise
Photomedicine**
- 10:45 – 11:15** **Inga Morkvėnaitė-Vilkončienė** (Vilnius Gediminas Technical
University, Lithuania)
**Scanning Electrochemical Microscopy as a Tool for the
Visualization of Antigen and Antibody Interaction**
- 11:15 – 11:45** **Gil Rosenman** (Tel Aviv University, Israel)
StartUP Companies: Hopes and Reality
- 11:45 – 12:00** **Closing remarks**
- 12:00 – 13:00** **Meeting of Project H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 Marie
Skłodowska-Curie Action: Research and Innovation Staff
Exchange - Grant Agreement 778308 - SPINMULTIFILM:
“Physical Principles of the Creation of Novel SPINtronic
Materials on the Base of MULTIlayered Metal-Oxide FILMs
for Magnetic Sensors and MRAM”**

P99. Penetration of Esters, Derived from Vegetable Oils, into Anodized Coating for Friction Reduction

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Rapidly advancing metathesis processes yield a great variety of esters, which can be manufactured from vegetable oils or Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME). Esters, produced from non-food oils, such as Crambe and Camelina, are of particular interest. Some of these compounds are effective in reducing friction on anodized alumina [1]. They act as nanopore fillers by penetrating into the coating and assuring formation of a lubricant layer in the friction zone. However, it is difficult to determine how deep the esters penetrate into the Type III coating, fig. 1. Conventional elemental analysis, such as XPS or EDX, cannot yield unambiguous profiles due to uncertainty of C, H and O origins [2].

Fig. 1. Surface (A) and cross-section (B) of anodized Al alloy 1050. The scheme (C) shows calculated coating parameters

Several innovative techniques were used in efforts to establish the concentration gradients. FAME were spiked with a fluorophore Rhodamine B and then impregnated into the coating on a metal disc of ~1 mm thickness. Confocal fluorescent microscopy showed that the penetration depths approached 30 microns [3]. Raman spectroscopy was also used to monitor the diffusion of aqueous chromium-based azodyes into anodized foil of less than 0.1 mm thickness [4]. These techniques can be employed for the measurement of ester migration in anodized coatings and correlation to tribological properties.

Keywords: esters, anodized alumina, penetration.

Acknowledgements: The project COSMOS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 635405.

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**ADVANCED MATERIALS AND TECHNOLOGIES
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
OF THE 21st INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE-SCHOOL**

ISSN 1822-7759

SL 344. 2019-07-19. 10,25 leidyb. apsk. l. Tiražas 162 egz.

Kaina sutartinė. Užsakymas 174.

Išleido Kauno technologijos universitetas, K. Donelaičio g. 73, 44029 Kaunas
Spausdino leidyklos „Technologija“ spaustuvė, Studentų g. 54, 51424 Kaunas